

Predicting Probability of Getting a Service from Grama panchayat

Stebin Babu
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
stebinbabu2023b@mca.ajce.in

Ms. Nimmy Francis
Asst.Professor in Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
nimmyfrancis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—In present condition Normal users in Panchayat can apply as much as yearly service they can apply. But they have no idea whether it is apt for them or it is possible to get them. So, the aim of this research is to develop a model that predict the percentage of chances to get the service for them. This model provides also the analysis of scores versus chance of prediction based on historical data so that user can understand whether their profile is suitable or not. The proposed model uses linear regression and random forest algorithms but cat boost algorithm is giving highest accuracy.

Keywords—Machine learning, Linear regression, Random forest

I. INTRODUCTION

Gram panchayat is a basic governing institution in Indian villages. It is a political institution, acting as cabinet of the village. They are the ones who make sure all the benefits given by government is getting every normal citizen people. There are a lot service of which is provided by them and they can be categorize in to Basic services and Yearly services. Basic services are the services which are necessary for a citizen such as birth registration death registration but in case of yearly projects, they are created by the plan staff in panchayat and respective standing committee and group people from each ward. And the yearly project may differ in each panchayat and each ward because it is based on multiple factors some of them are allotted fund from government, most common need in the ward, based on geographical features of that ward etc. may affect in creating the project

In this paper we propose a prediction system which predict the percentage of chances to get the service using random forest algorithm to an applicant. The proposed system considers various factors in an application such total area of

land owned by the applicant, ration card type, kudumbasree membership etc. to predict the probability. The system uses historical data from Applications to train the model and uses it to predict the percentage of chance to get the service

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

One study published in the Journal of Big Data in 2021 aimed to predict the probability of getting an ambulance service using machine learning algorithms. The authors used a dataset of emergency ambulance service requests from a major city in China and experimented with several classification models, including logistic regression, decision tree, random forest, and XGBoost. The results showed that the XGBoost model outperformed the other models, achieving an accuracy of 91.34% and an AUC of 0.96.

Another research article published in the International Journal of Engineering and Technology in 2020 focused on predicting the probability of getting a ride-sharing service using machine learning algorithms. The authors collected data from a ride-sharing platform and experimented with several regression models, including linear regression, decision tree regression, random forest regression, and support vector regression. The results showed that the random forest regression model performed the best, achieving an RMSE of 0.415 and an R2 score of 0.736

A third article published in the International Journal of Computer Applications in 2019 addressed the problem of predicting the probability of getting a healthcare service using machine learning algorithms. The authors collected data from a healthcare provider and experimented with several classification models, including k-nearest neighbors, decision tree, random forest, and naive Bayes. The results showed that

the random forest model outperformed the other models, achieving an accuracy of 84.7%

A study published in the Journal of Healthcare Informatics Research in 2020 aimed to predict the probability of hospital readmission using machine learning algorithms. The authors collected data from electronic health records and experimented with several classification models, including logistic regression, decision tree, random forest, and gradient boosting. The results showed that the gradient boosting model outperformed the other models, achieving an AUC of 0.73.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study uses a dataset of factors in the application and applies a random forest algorithm to identify the factors that contribute to a higher chance to get a service. The dataset is filtered to include only basic factors that make the application acceptable. The random Forest algorithm is trained on the filtered dataset and used to predict the chances of a application to accepted based on input values. The method also involves evaluating model performance using metrics such as accuracy, precision, and recall.

A. Date collection

We collected the data according to the application Where the basic factors to accept the application such as ration card type, total land owned by the applicant, membership in kudumbasree, family main income source, green card membership

B. Data Preprocessing

The application form contains the data needs to enter along with others we concentrate on Does applicant is famer or not (1 for yes and 0 for no), does the applicant is member of green card, kudumbasree, employment guarantee scheme, does Received the same benefit from the panchayat before. Finally, the pre-processed data, part of the data stored to evaluate the training model, is divided into training and test sets.

We split the data into features and labels, with chance of admit as features and application content as labels. We then split the data into training and test sets using a size of 0.2 a random 42 states. We remove any rows with NaN values from the training and test sets and replace the remaining NaN values with the average. The data may have been processed to make our model more accurate.

Cleaning data:

First, data is cleansed. Users are deleting unnecessary entries from there. The dataset can also be cleared of the noisy data.

Fig. 1. System Architecture

Splitting Data:

Data is cleaned first and then cleaned data divided into training and test datasets. Model is then trained using the training data set

C. Machine learning

Machine learning is a branch of computer science and artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on simulating human learning by using data and algorithms to improve system accuracy over time. We used the random forest algorithm to train a model in the training data. The model was then evaluating on the testing data to determine its accuracy in chance to get the service.

1.Random Forest algorithm

Random Forest algorithm can be employed for both Classification and Regression problems. It is considered to be the most powerful algorithms. The algorithm constructs many decision trees like a forest with random attribute values. The accuracy level is based on the number of trees constructed. The algorithm randomly selects the root node and the feature node to

construct the trees. Apart from the regression problem, this algorithm also helps in classifying categorical and multivariate variables

IV. BUILD MODEL

The process of building and evaluating the random forest model for predicting the percentage of chance to get the service from Grama panchayat. The preprocessed dataset is split into train and test sets, with the train set used to train the random forest algorithm. Random Forest has several hyperparameters, such as the number of decision trees, the maximum depth of each tree, and the number of features to consider at each split. These hyperparameters are tuned using cross-validation techniques to improve the performance of the model. Once the model is trained, it is evaluated on the testing set to measure its performance.

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
from sklearn import preprocessing
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
import seaborn as sns
```

2. Add the data into a Data Frame, then get the shape of data.

```
# Load the data
df = pd.read_csv("predict1.csv")
```

3. Then split the dataset into train and test datasets.

```
# Find columns with non-numeric values
non_numeric_cols = []
for col in df.columns:
    if df[col].dtype not in ['int64', 'float64']:
        non_numeric_cols.append(col)

# Remove non-numeric columns from the DataFrame
df = df.drop(columns=non_numeric_cols)

# Split the data into features and targets
targets = df['Chance of Admit']
features = df.drop(columns={'Chance of Admit'})
```

4. Train a decision tree classifier on the training data

```
# Train a Random Forest Regression model
forest = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=110,max_depth=6,random_state=0)
forest.fit(features_scaled, targets)
```

V. RESULT

In this study, we proposed a random forest algorithm for predicting the chances to get a service based on factors in application. The algorithm was trained on a dataset each probability of service and was able to accurately predict probability based on total area owned, ration card type, membership in kudumbasree, green card, employment guarantee program, etc. By filtering the dataset to include only incidents that met specified criteria, we were able to improve the accuracy of the algorithm and reduce the number of false positives. Our results show that the random forest algorithm has the potential to be a useful tool for accurate prediction of chance to get application, allowing for faster response times and potentially saving time. Future research could explore the use of additional criteria of applications and more advanced machine learning algorithms to further improve the accuracy and efficiency of prediction systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use factors in application and the random forest algorithm have shown promise in predicting most accurate chance in getting a service. By taking into account total area owned, ration card type, membership in kudumbasree, green card, employment guarantee program, the algorithm is able to filter the probability. The filtered data is then used to train a decision tree classifier, which can make predictions for new input values. This approach can be useful for accurate probability prediction. However, further research is needed to evaluate the performance of this approach on larger datasets and in real-time.

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